

ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS (SDGS) THROUGH EFFECTIVE ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION PROGRAMME IN SOUTH-EAST, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study was carried out to determine strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Entrepreneurship Education programme in South-East, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. A survey research design was used for the study. The population for the study consisted of 80 Business Educators from Federal and State owned universities in South-East. There was no sampling because the population size was not too large. A-20 item structured questionnaire developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts; while Cronbach Alpha was used to determine its reliability coefficient with an overall index value of 0.80. Mean with standard deviation was used to answer the research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant using t-test statistic. Findings showed that institutional and Lecturers related strategies are needed to achieve sustainable development Goals through effective Entrepreneurship Education programme in South-East. Again, there was no significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators in Federal and State owned universities on institutional and Lecturers related strategies respectively for achieving SDGs. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that, there should be constant review of Entrepreneurship Education curriculum to meet global goals.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship Education, Sustainable Development, Effectiveness, Strategies, Achievement.*

Introduction

One of the duties of any responsible government irrespective of the country is to provide her citizens with the needed democratic dividends. Globally, citizens of these countries particularly Nigeria seem to be facing hunger, insecurity, unemployment, poor quality education among others.

In an attempt to overcome the above challenges, 193 countries in September 2015 came together at United Nations to adopt comprehensive strategy to tackle challenges related global sustainable development. According to United Nations (2015), sustainable development is an approach to growth

and human development that aims to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It is the ability to manage withstand and continue in spite of any circumstances and not solely economic growth or human development but both. Hence, the 5ps of sustainable development of people, planet, property, peace and partnership Salami (2019). Based on the above, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or Global Goals was designed.

The Sustainable Development Goals according to Ghost and Chakavarty (2024) were launched in 2015 by the United Nations as a global initiative aimed at eradicating poverty, safe-guarding the environment, and promoting peace and prosperity for all by 2030, as outlined in the United Nations 2030 Agenda: SDGs therefore emphasize the interconnected environmental, social and economic aspect of sustainable development by putting sustainability at their centre.

Achieving the SDGs requires collective efforts from the governments, businesses, civil society and individuals. According to Biemann, Frank, Hickmann, Senit and Carole (2022), there are seventeen (17) SDGs, which range from No poverty to partnership. Infact, the 17 SDGs include: No poverty, zero hunger, Good Health and Well-being, Quality Education, Gender Equality, Clean water and Sanitation, Affordable and clean Energy, Decent work and Economic Growth. It also include Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Reduced inequalities, Sustainable cities and communities, Responsible consumption and production, Climate Action, Life Below Water, Life on Land, Peace, Justice and strong institutions and partnerships for the Goals.

Moreover, these goals are synonymous with Entrepreneurship Education; which is for wealth, job creation, and sustainability among others. It is vital to have effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme in universities. Looking at the goals of SDGs carefully, it can be concluded that, if there any Education to achieve Sustainable Development Goals, it is Entrepreneurship Education.

Entrepreneurship Education according to Eya and Ugwunwoti (2022) is the process of teaching and learning entrepreneurial skills, mindset and knowledge to individuals, often with the goal of starting and running their own businesses or ventures. Entrepreneurship education is about developing the skills, knowledge, and attitudes necessary to identify and exploit entrepreneurial opportunities. Sane and Venkataraman (2022), opined that Entrepreneurship Education is the process of teaching and learning entrepreneurial skills, knowledge and mindset to individuals. Entrepreneurial mindset is a way of thinking that enables one to overcome challenges, be decisive and accept responsibility for ones outcomes (Eya and Ugwunwoti, 2022). Moreso, one of the objectives of Entrepreneurship Education particularly in universities is to equip students to be employers of labour instead of job-seekers. The realization of these objectives is largely dependent on the strategies applicable.

Strategies are long-term plans of action designed to achieve specific goals of objectives. In Entrepreneurship Education programme, strategies refers to deliberate plans and approaches to achieve specific learning objectives, enhance students engagement, and develop essential skills for future

entrepreneurs (Ugwunwoti, 2024). For this study, institutional and Lecturers related strategies will be discussed.

One of the strategies for achieving SDGs through effective Entrepreneurship Education programme is Institutional related strategies. In Entrepreneurship Education, strategies refer to the approaches and initiatives implemented by educational institutions to foster entrepreneurial mindset, skills and knowledge among students. Chibuike (2023) noted that if universities that have the Entrepreneurship Education programme must achieve their goals; they must put in place quality enhancing strategies that will ensure the production of quality graduates for National development. By implementing Institutional-related strategies, universities can play a crucial role in fostering entrepreneurship and supporting the next generation of entrepreneurs. Apart from institutional strategies, Lecturers-related strategies will help in achieving SDGs.

Lecturers-related strategies in entrepreneurship education refer to the approaches and techniques used by lecturers to teach and support students in developing entrepreneurial skills and mindset. A lecturer is an academic Professional who teaches and delivers educational content to students in a specific, subject area, often in Universities. Overall, lecturers play a vital role in shaping the educational experience and helping students achieve their academic goals. In this study, Lecturers are called Business Educators. A Business Educators according to Njoku (2020) are professionals who teach and train students in business-related subjects, such as management, marketing, Finance, accounting and entrepreneurship.

Ugwunwoti and Eya (2020), opined that Business Educators is the implementer of curriculum; decides on what instructional materials to use; the method to adopt, the amount of time to spend on each aspect and the equipment as well as space to use.

In South-East States of Nigeria, Business Educators are employed by both the state and federal universities. State universities are owned, financed and controlled by the state government. On the other hand, federal universities are owned, financed and controlled by the federal government (Agbo and Ugwunwoti, 2022). These educators irrespective of the ownership of the universities are expected to pursue effective entrepreneurship education programme.

Achieving effectiveness is the technique or mechanism put in place to bring about a degree of excellence of a product or services. According to Onyesom and Umoeshiet (2023). Achieving effectiveness in Entrepreneurship Education refers to the degree to which entrepreneurship education programs, initiatives or strategies achieve their intended goals and objectives. When there is effective Entrepreneurship Education, SDGs can be achievable by promoting innovation and creativity, encouraging sustainable business practices, developing entrepreneurial skills, fostering economic growth and fostering and addressing social challenges.

There is a pressing need for effective Entrepreneurship Education in South East Nigeria that addresses the region's specific challenges and promotes sustainable development. This could be achievable through

strategies. It is upon this background, the need arose to determine the strategies for achieving sustainable Development Goals through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme in South-East, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Education is the process of acquiring knowledge, skills and values, through learning and experiences, Entrepreneurship Education in other hand is training that equip the individuals with competencies to be employers of labour instead of job-seekers.

No wonder, the SDGs November 4 (Quality Education) to ensure inclusive and equitable education was captured. With Entrepreneurship Education, zero hunger, No poverty, decent work and economic growth among others will be achieved. Thus, prevent missed opportunities for economic growth and unsustainable unemployment.

Despite the potential of entrepreneurship education to drive SDGs, South-East Nigeria seem to be facing significant challenges in achieving SDGs. The region seems to be struggling with high unemployment rates, limited economic opportunities and inadequate Infrastructure, hindering the growth of entrepreneurship and sustainable development. Hence, this aim for carrying out this work achieving SDGs through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme in South -East, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme in South East States. Specifically the study sought to:

1. ascertain the institutional-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme in South- East ,Nigeria.
2. determine the lecturers-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme in South -East Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study,

1. What are the institutional -related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme in South -East, Nigeria?
2. What are the lecturers -related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme in South -East, Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test.

H01: There is a significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators in Federal and State universities on institutional-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme in South -East, Nigeria.

H02: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators in Federal and State universities in South -East regarding the lecturers-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme.

Method

Descriptive research design was adopted for the study and the study was carried out in South East Nigeria. The population for the study comprised 80 Business Educators in the universities offering Business Education (Entrepreneurship) in the zone. No sampling was done because the researcher found the population of the study to be manageable. The instrument for data collection was a structured Questionnaire developed by the researchers titled: "Achieving Sustainable Development Goals Questionnaire (ASDGQ)". The instrument was structured on a four-point rating scale of: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument has two sections: A and B, section A contained Bio- data of the respondents while section B contained 20 items in two clusters.

Cluster B1 contained 10 items on the institutional related strategies, while Cluster B2 contained 10 items on lecturers-related strategies. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education and one from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education, all from Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT). The instrument was subjected to a pilot test on 20 Business Educators in South-south. The application of Cronbach Alpha reliability test on the returned data yielded coefficient values of 0.81 and 0.78 for Clusters B1 and B2 respectively with an overall reliability coefficient value of 0.80 for the two Clusters.

The researchers administered 80 copies of the instrument through email and WhatsApp respectively to the respondents. There was 100 percent return rate. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t-test. The mean value was used to answer the research questions, while the standard deviation was used to ascertain the homogeneity or otherwise of the respondents responses. In analyzing the mean, any item with mean score between the 2.50 to 4.00 was deemed to be agreed while any item with mean score between 2.49 and 1.00 was disagreed. For the hypotheses, t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Where the calculated t-value was less than the critical value of t, it meant that the variable did not significantly affect responses and the hypothesis was accepted. Conversely, where the calculated value of t-value, it meant that the variable had a significant effect on the respondents mean responses and the hypothesis was rejected .

RESULTS:

Research Question 1

What are the institutional-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme in South East, Nigeria?

Table1: Mean responses and standard deviation of Business Educators on the institutional-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals in South East, Nigeria.

S/N	Items on Institutional-related strategies	Federal N=60		State N=20		Overall N=80		Decision
		X1	SD1	X2	SD2	X	SD	
1	Incorporate entrepreneurship education into the curriculum of tertiary institutions	3.41	0.90	3.35	0.82	3.23	0.86	Agree
2	Collaborate with industries to provide students with practical experience	3.58	0.84	3.45	0.87	3.52	0.71	Agree
3	Establish mentorship programs that pair students with experienced entrepreneurs	3.60	0.49	3.32	0.71	3.43	0.66	Agree
4	Encourage innovation among students through incubation centers	3.57	0.50	3.33	0.89	3.45	0.77	Agree
5	Develop entrepreneurship focused research centers	3.28	0.72	3.52	0.57	3.40	0.60	Agree
6	Offer access to funding to support students entrepreneurship projects	3.40	0.66	3.25	0.75	3.33	0.71	Agree
7	Organize networking events to connect students with entrepreneurs	3.28	0.72	3.52	0.57	3.34	0.63	Agree
8	Design training programs that equip students with practical skills	3.25	0.75	3.40	0.66	3.32	0.71	Agree
9	Engage with local communities to promote entrepreneurship	3.35	0.82	3.14	0.90	3.25	0,86	Agree
10	10. Regular evaluation of entrepreneurship programs to ensure they are meeting their objectives	3.60	0.49	3.32	0.71	3.43	0.66	Agree
Cluster mean/SD		3.41	0.68	3.27	0.76	3.34	0.76	Agree

The result in Table 1 above shows that, the respondents (Business Educators) in Federal and State Universities in South-East, Nigeria agreed that Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) could be achieved through effective Entrepreneurship Education programme. Their mean scores range from 3.25 to 3.45; showing agreement since the mean value cut-off was 2.50. Their standard deviation also ranges from 0.60 to 0.86. This is an indication that their responses were close or homogeneous

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities on Institutional-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Entrepreneurship Education in South-East, Nigeria.

Table 2: Summary Table of t-test of analysis of mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities in South-East, Nigeria on Institutional-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Entrepreneurship Education programme

Respondents	No	\bar{x}	SD	df	t-cal	t-tab	Decision
Federal	60	3.41	0.68	78	0.36	1.96	Not significant
State	20	3.27	0.76				
Total	80						

Table 2 above shows that, the calculated table at 0.05 level of significance and 78 degree of freedom was 0.36; while the t-test under the same condition was 1.96. Since the calculated t-value was less than the table value, the null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This invariably means that, Business Educators in Federal and State Universities in South-East, Nigeria did not differ significantly in their mean scores on the Institutional-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Entrepreneurship Education programme

Research Question 2

What are the Lecturers-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Entrepreneurship Education programme in South-East, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean scores and standard deviation of Business Educators in universities on Lecturers-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Entrepreneurship Education programme in South-East, Nigeria

S/N	Items on Lecturers-related strategies	Federal		State		Overall		Decision
		N=60		N=20		N=80		
		X1	SD1	X2	SD2	X	SD	
11	Integrate SDGs into entrepreneurship education curriculum to raise awareness	3.60	0.58	3.59	0.60	3.60	0.59	Agree
12	Use experiential learning methods to equip students with practical skills	3.15	1.03	3.49	0.71	3.32	0.81	Agree
13	Foster students-centered learning approach	2.86	0.97	2.92	0.96	2.89	0.97	Agree
14	Use real-world examples to illustrate							

	entrepreneurship	3.20	0.79	3.12	0.82	3.16	0.81	Agree
15	Provide one-on-one mentorship to students	3.26	0.83	3.26	0.85	3.26	0.84	Agree
16	Encourage collaboration among students to promote knowledge sharing	3.23	0.83	3.35	0.59	3.29	0.61	Agree
17	Leverage technology to enhance entrepreneurship education	3.48	0.71	3.47	0.60	3.48	0.63	Agree
18	Emphasize social entrepreneurship	3.49	0.59	3.15	1.03	3.32	0.55	Agree
19	Provide regular assessment to students	3.35	0.77	3.23	0.66	3.29	0.89	Agree
20	Stay updated with industry trends	3.25	0.80	3.31	0.73	3.29	0.63	Agree
	Cluster mean/SD	3.29	0.76	3.80	0.67	3.56	0.72	Agree

Data presented in Table 3 above shows, the mean scores of the respondents (Business Educators in universities in South-East, Nigeria) for the items on Lecturers-related strategies. The mean scores for items number 11 is Strongly Agree (SA) with 3.60. The remaining 12-20 are "agree". The aggregate mean score ranges from 3.16 to 3.60 and the grand mean of 3.56; also attested to that. The cluster standard deviation of 0.72 shows that the disparities of opinions of the respondents are slim.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities in South-East regarding the Lecturers-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Entrepreneurship Education programme.

Table 4: Summary Table of t-test analysis of difference between the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities in South-East on Lecturers-related strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals through effective Entrepreneurship Education programme

Respondents	No	\bar{x}	SD	df	t-cal	t-tab	Decision
Male	60	3.29	0.76	78	0.53	1.96	Not significant
Female	20	3.80	0.67				
Total	80						

Table 4 shows that, the calculated t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 78 degree of freedom is 0.58; while the critical t-Value under the same condition is 1.96. Since the calculated t-value is less than the table value, the null hypothesis is therefore not significant.

This means that, the mean scores of Business Educators in Federal and State universities in South-East, Nigeria did not differ significantly on the Lecturers-related Strategies for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme.

Discussion of the Findings

The data presented in Table 1, showed that Business Educators in Federal and State Universities in South East Nigeria were in agreement that Institutional-related strategies are needed in achieving SDGs through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme. These strategies are incorporate Entrepreneurship Education into the curriculum into universities, collaborate with industries to provide students with practical experience among others.

The findings are in line with Chibuike (2023) that if universities that have the Entrepreneurship Education programme must achieve their goals; they must put in place quality enhancing strategies that will ensure the production of quality graduates for national development.

The null hypothesis tested on institutional-related strategies showed that, there was no significant difference between scores of Business Educators in Federal and State Universities respectively on institutional-related strategies for achieving SDGs through Effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme in South East, Nigeria. The implications of the findings of no significant difference was that, the status of university had no significant influence in their opinions.

Data obtained regarding research questions two, revealed that Business Educators in Federal and State universities in South-East were in agreement that Lecturers-related strategies are needed for achieving SDGs through effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme. The findings where in harmony with Ugwunwoti and Eya (2020) that opined that Business Educators is the implementer of curriculum; decides on what instructional materials to use and the method(s) to adopt.

The null hypothesis two tested showed that Business Educators in Federal and State universities did not differ significantly in their mean scores on Lecturers-related strategies for achieving SDGs through effective Entrepreneurship Education programme. The implication of the findings of no significant difference was that the status of the universities had no significant influence in their opinions.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that effective Entrepreneurship Education Programme can play a vital role in achieving SDGs by; fostering sustainable economic growth (SDG 8 Decent Work and Economic Growth). Promotes quality education (SDG4, Quality Education) and addressing environmental challenges SDG 13 (Climate Action).

Recommendations

Base on the findings and conclusion, it was recommended that:

1. Authority concern should integrate Entrepreneurship Education into curricula, focusing on developing entrepreneurship skills and mindset.

2. There should be continuous professional development opportunities to equip educators with innovative strategies that should be organized by the institutions.

3. Universities should establish mentorship Programmes that pair students with experienced entrepreneurs.

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